

Coordination of Electricity, Heat and Natural Gas Systems Accounting for Network Flexibility

Online Appendix

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This document serves as an electronic companion for the paper “Coordination of Electricity, Heat and Natural Gas Systems Accounting for Network Flexibility”. It contains the nomenclature, Section 1 presents the detailed formulation of mixed-integer second-order cone program (MISOCP) from the original manuscript, and Section 2 gives the technical characteristics of power generators, gas suppliers, and heat stations for the case study presented in the paper.

NOMENCLATURE

Sets

- \mathcal{I} Set of dispatchable generation units i .
- \mathcal{C} Subset of dispatchable power plants excluding natural gas-fired ones ($\mathcal{C} \subset \mathcal{I}$).
- \mathcal{G} Subset of natural gas-fired power plants ($\mathcal{G} \subset \mathcal{I}$).
- \mathcal{J} Set of wind power units j .
- \mathcal{CHP} Subset of combined heat and power plants ($\mathcal{CHP} \subset \mathcal{HS} \subset \mathcal{I}$).
- \mathcal{HP} Subset of heat pumps ($\mathcal{HP} \subset \mathcal{HS} \subset \mathcal{I}$).
- \mathcal{HS} Subset of heat stations ($\mathcal{HS} \subset \mathcal{I}$).
- \mathcal{HES} Set of heat exchange stations o .
- \mathcal{T} Set of time periods t .
- \mathcal{L} Set of electricity transmission lines (n, r) .
- \mathcal{N} Set of electricity network nodes n .
- \mathcal{O} Set of heat network nodes o .
- \mathcal{P} Set of heat pipelines (o, v) .
- \mathcal{K} Set of natural gas supply units k .
- \mathcal{Z} Set of natural gas pipelines (m, u) .
- \mathcal{M} Set of natural gas network nodes m .
- $\mathcal{A}_n^{(\cdot)}$ Set of assets located at electricity network node n .
- $\mathcal{A}_o^{(\cdot)}$ Set of assets located at heat network node o .
- $\mathcal{A}_m^{(\cdot)}$ Set of assets located at natural gas network node m .
- Θ Set of optimization variables.

Variables

- $p_{i,t}$ Power dispatch of units i in period t [MW].
- $w_{j,t}$ Dispatch of units j in period t [MW].
- $Q_{i,t}$ Heat dispatch of units i in period t [MW].
- $g_{k,t}$ Dispatch of unit k in period t [kcf/h].
- $\theta_{n,t}$ Voltage angle at node n in period t [rad].
- $f_{n,r,t}$ Power flow in line (n, r) in period t [MW].
- $pr_{m,t}$ Pressure at node m in period t [psig].
- $h_{m,u,t}$ Average mass of natural gas (linepack) in pipeline (m, u) in period t [kcf].
- $q_{m,u,t}^{\text{in/out}}$ Inflow/outflow natural gas rate of pipeline (m, u) in period t [kcf/h].
- $q_{m,u,t}$ Natural gas flow in pipeline (m, u) in period t [kcf/h].
- $m_{o,t}^{\text{HES}}$ Heat exchanger mass flows at network node o in period t [kg m^{-3}].
- $m_{i,t}^{\text{HS}}$ Mass flows at heat station i in period t [kg m^{-3}].

- $T_{o,t}^S$ Temperature at supply network node o in period t [K].
 $T_{o,t}^R$ Temperature at return network node o in period t [K].
 $T_{o,v,t}^{S,in}$ Temperature at the entrance of the pipe (o, v) in period t [K].
 $T_{o,v,t}^{R,in}$ Temperature at the entrance of the pipe (o, v) in period t [K].
 $T_{o,v,t}^{S,out}$ Temperature at the outlet of the pipe (o, v) in period t [K].
 $T_{o,v,t}^{R,out}$ Temperature at the outlet of the pipe (o, v) in period t [K].
 $pr_{o,t}^S$ Pressure at supply network node o in period t [psig].
 $pr_{o,t}^R$ Pressure at return network node o in period t [psig].
 $D_{i,t}^{HP}$ Power consumption of heat pump i in period t [MWh].
 $\tau_{o,v,t}^{S/R}$ Time delay of heat propagation in supply and return pipeline (o, v) in period t [h].
 $u_{o,v,\eta,t}^{S/R}$ Auxiliary binary variable defining varying time delays in pipeline (o, v) in period $t \in \{0,1\}$.
 $v_{o,v,\eta,t}^{S/R}$ Auxiliary binary variable defining varying time delays in pipeline (o, v) in period $t \in \{0,1\}$.

Parameters

- $D_{n,t}^E$ Electricity demand at node n in period t [MWh].
 $D_{o,t}^H$ Heat demand at node o in period t [MWh].
 $D_{m,t}^G$ Natural gas demand at node m in period t [kcf/h].
 C_i^E Power production cost of unit i [\$/MWh].
 C_i^H Heat production cost of unit i [\$/MWh].
 C_i Marginal production cost of unit i [\$/MWh].
 C_k^G Supply cost of unit k [\$/kcf].
 \bar{p}_i Capacity of dispatchable unit i [MW].
 \bar{Q}_i Capacity of dispatchable unit i [MW].
 ρ_i^E Electricity fuel efficiency of CHP unit $i \in \mathcal{CHP}$.
 ρ_i^H Heat fuel efficiency of CHP unit $i \in \mathcal{CHP}$.
 pr_o^{HES} Minimum pressure gradient at heat exchanger station node o [psig].
 r_i Output ratio of unit $i \in \mathcal{CHP}$.
 COP_i Coefficient of performance of unit $i \in \mathcal{HP}$.
 ϕ_i Power conversion factor of natural gas unit $i \in \mathcal{G}$ [kcf/MWh].
 $\bar{w}_{j,t}$ Wind power realization for unit j in period t [MW].
 \bar{g}_k Capacity of natural gas unit k [kcf].
 $B_{n,r}$ Susceptance of line (n, r) [S].
 $\bar{f}_{n,r}$ Transmission capacity of line (n, r) [MW].
 $K_{m,u}$ Natural gas flow constant of pipeline (m, u) [kcf/psig].
 $S_{m,u}$ Linepack constant of pipeline (m, u) [kcf/(psig h)].
 $H_{m,u}^0$ Initial linepack in pipeline (m, u) [kcf].
 pr_o^S Minimum pressure at supply network node o [psig].
 \bar{pr}_o^S Maximum pressure at supply network node o [psig].
 pr_o^R Minimum pressure at return network node o [psig].
 \bar{pr}_o^R Maximum pressure at return network node o [psig].
 \underline{T}_o^S Minimum temperature at supply network node o [K].
 \bar{T}_o^S Maximum temperature at supply network node o [K].
 \underline{T}_o^R Minimum temperature at return network node o [K].
 \bar{T}_o^R Maximum temperature at return network node o [K].
 $\underline{m}_o^{\text{HES}}$ Minimum mass flow at heat exchange station o [kg/h].
 \bar{m}_o^{HES} Maximum mass flow at heat exchange station o [kg/h].
 $\underline{m}_i^{\text{HS}}$ Minimum mass flow at heat station $i \in \mathcal{HS}$ [kg/h].
 \bar{m}_i^{HS} Maximum mass flow at heat station $i \in \mathcal{HS}$ [kg/h].
 $\underline{m}_{o,v}^S$ Minimum mass flow in supply pipeline $(o, v) \in \mathcal{P}$ [kg/h].
 $\bar{m}_{o,v}^S$ Maximum mass flow in supply pipeline $(o, v) \in \mathcal{P}$ [kg/h].
 $\underline{m}_{o,v}^R$ Minimum mass flow in return pipeline $(o, v) \in \mathcal{P}$ [kg/h].
 $\bar{m}_{o,v}^R$ Maximum mass flow in return pipeline $(o, v) \in \mathcal{P}$ [kg/h].

- $L_{o,v}$ Pressure loss coefficient pipeline $(o, v) \in \mathcal{P}$.
 \underline{pr}_m Minimum pressure limit at node m [psig].
 \overline{pr}_m Maximum pressure limit at node m [psig].
 $\Gamma_{m,u}$ Compressor factor at natural gas pipeline (m, u) .
 c Specific heat capacity of water [$\text{J kg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$].
 $\mu_{o,v}$ Thermal loss coefficient [$\text{J m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$].
 ρ Water density [kg m^{-3}].
 $R_{o,v}$ Radius of the pipeline (o, v) [m].
 $\overline{\tau}_{o,v}^{\text{S,R}}$ Maximum time delay parameters of pipeline (o, v) .
 M A sufficiently large positive constant.

1. MISOCP FOR THE INTEGRATED MULTI-ENERGY DISPATCH

$$\min_{\Theta} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{C}} C_i^{\text{E}} p_{i,t} + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} C_k^{\text{G}} g_{k,t} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{HS}} C_i^{\text{H}} Q_{i,t} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{CHP}} C_i (\rho_i^{\text{E}} p_{i,t} + \rho_i^{\text{H}} Q_{i,t}) \right), \quad (1a)$$

subject to

$$0 \leq p_{i,t} \leq \overline{p}_i, \forall i, t, \quad (1b)$$

$$0 \leq w_{j,t} \leq \overline{w}_{j,t}, \forall j, t, \quad (1c)$$

$$f_{n,r,t} = B_{n,r}(\theta_{n,t} - \theta_{r,t}), \forall (n, r) \in \mathcal{L}, t, \quad (1d)$$

$$-\overline{f}_{n,r} \leq f_{n,r,t} \leq \overline{f}_{n,r}, \forall (n, r) \in \mathcal{L}, t, \quad (1e)$$

$$-\pi \leq \theta_{n,t} \leq \pi, \forall n, t, \quad \theta_{n,t} = 0, \forall n : \text{ref}, t, \quad (1f)$$

$$D_{o,t}^{\text{H}} \geq c \overline{mf}_o^{\text{HES}} (T_{o,t}^{\text{S}} - T_{o,t}^{\text{R}}) + c mf_{o,t}^{\text{HES}} (\overline{T}_o^{\text{S}} - \underline{T}_o^{\text{R}}) - c \overline{mf}_o^{\text{HES}} (\overline{T}_o^{\text{S}} - \underline{T}_o^{\text{R}}), \forall o, t, \quad (1g)$$

$$D_{o,t}^{\text{H}} \geq c \underline{mf}_o^{\text{HES}} (T_{o,t}^{\text{S}} - T_{o,t}^{\text{R}}) + c mf_{o,t}^{\text{HES}} (\underline{T}_o^{\text{S}} - \overline{T}_o^{\text{R}}) - c \underline{mf}_o^{\text{HES}} (\underline{T}_o^{\text{S}} - \overline{T}_o^{\text{R}}), \forall o, t, \quad (1h)$$

$$D_{o,t}^{\text{H}} \leq c \overline{mf}_o^{\text{HES}} (T_{o,t}^{\text{S}} - T_{o,t}^{\text{R}}) + c mf_{o,t}^{\text{HES}} (\underline{T}_o^{\text{S}} - \overline{T}_o^{\text{R}}) - c \overline{mf}_o^{\text{HES}} (\underline{T}_o^{\text{S}} - \overline{T}_o^{\text{R}}), \forall o, t, \quad (1i)$$

$$D_{o,t}^{\text{H}} \leq c \underline{mf}_o^{\text{HES}} (T_{o,t}^{\text{S}} - T_{o,t}^{\text{R}}) + c mf_{o,t}^{\text{HES}} (\overline{T}_o^{\text{S}} - \underline{T}_o^{\text{R}}) - c \underline{mf}_o^{\text{HES}} (\overline{T}_o^{\text{S}} - \underline{T}_o^{\text{R}}), \forall o, t, \quad (1j)$$

$$Q_{i,t} \geq c \overline{mf}_i^{\text{HS}} (T_{o,t}^{\text{S}} - T_{o,t}^{\text{R}}) + c mf_{i,t}^{\text{HS}} (\overline{T}_o^{\text{S}} - \underline{T}_o^{\text{R}}) - c \overline{mf}_i^{\text{HS}} (\overline{T}_o^{\text{S}} - \underline{T}_o^{\text{R}}), \forall o, i \in \mathcal{A}_o^{\text{HS}}, t, \quad (1k)$$

$$Q_{i,t} \geq c \underline{mf}_i^{\text{HS}} (T_{o,t}^{\text{S}} - T_{o,t}^{\text{R}}) + c mf_{i,t}^{\text{HS}} (\underline{T}_o^{\text{S}} - \overline{T}_o^{\text{R}}) - c \underline{mf}_i^{\text{HS}} (\underline{T}_o^{\text{S}} - \overline{T}_o^{\text{R}}), \forall o, i \in \mathcal{A}_o^{\text{HS}}, t, \quad (1l)$$

$$Q_{i,t} \leq c \overline{mf}_i^{\text{HS}} (T_{o,t}^{\text{S}} - T_{o,t}^{\text{R}}) + c mf_{i,t}^{\text{HS}} (\underline{T}_o^{\text{S}} - \overline{T}_o^{\text{R}}) - c \overline{mf}_i^{\text{HS}} (\underline{T}_o^{\text{S}} - \overline{T}_o^{\text{R}}), \forall o, i \in \mathcal{A}_o^{\text{HS}}, t, \quad (1m)$$

$$Q_{i,t} \leq c \underline{mf}_i^{\text{HS}} (T_{o,t}^{\text{S}} - T_{o,t}^{\text{R}}) + c mf_{i,t}^{\text{HS}} (\overline{T}_o^{\text{S}} - \underline{T}_o^{\text{R}}) - c \underline{mf}_i^{\text{HS}} (\overline{T}_o^{\text{S}} - \underline{T}_o^{\text{R}}), \forall o, i \in \mathcal{A}_o^{\text{HS}}, t, \quad (1n)$$

$$0 \leq Q_{i,t} \leq \overline{Q}_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{HS}, t, \quad (1o)$$

$$\underline{pr}_o^{\text{HES}} \leq pr_{o,t}^{\text{S}} - pr_{o,t}^{\text{R}}, \forall o, t, \quad (1p)$$

$$\underline{mf}_o^{\text{HES}} \leq mf_{o,t}^{\text{HES}} \leq \overline{mf}_o^{\text{HES}}, \forall o, t, \quad (1q)$$

$$\underline{mf}_i^{\text{HS}} \leq mf_{i,t}^{\text{HS}} \leq \overline{mf}_i^{\text{HS}}, \forall i \in \mathcal{HS}, t, \quad (1r)$$

$$\underline{mf}_{o,v}^{\text{S}} \leq mf_{o,v,t}^{\text{S}} \leq \overline{mf}_{o,v}^{\text{S}}, \forall (o, v) \in \mathcal{P}, t, \quad (1s)$$

$$\underline{mf}_{o,v}^{\text{R}} \leq mf_{o,v,t}^{\text{R}} \leq \overline{mf}_{o,v}^{\text{R}}, \forall (o, v) \in \mathcal{P}, t, \quad (1t)$$

$$\sum_{v:(o,v) \in \mathcal{P}} mf_{v,o,t}^{\text{S}} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}_o^{\text{HS}}} mf_{i,t}^{\text{HS}} = \sum_{v:(o,v) \in \mathcal{P}} mf_{o,v,t}^{\text{S}} + mf_{o,t}^{\text{HES}}, \forall o, t, \quad (1u)$$

$$\sum_{v:(o,v) \in \mathcal{P}} mf_{v,o,t}^{\text{R}} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}_o^{\text{HS}}} mf_{i,t}^{\text{HS}} = \sum_{v:(o,v) \in \mathcal{P}} mf_{o,v,t}^{\text{R}} + mf_{o,t}^{\text{HES}}, \forall o, t, \quad (1v)$$

$$L_{o,v} (mf_{o,v,t}^{\text{S}})^2 \leq pr_{v,t}^{\text{S}} - pr_{o,t}^{\text{S}}, \forall (o, v) \in \mathcal{P}, t, \quad (1w)$$

$$L_{o,v}(mf_{o,v,t}^R)^2 \leq pr_{v,t}^R - pr_{o,t}^R, \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, t, \quad (1x)$$

$$\underline{pr}_o^S \leq pr_{o,t}^S \leq \overline{pr}_o^S, \quad \underline{pr}_o^R \leq pr_{o,t}^R \leq \overline{pr}_o^R, \forall o, t, \quad (1y)$$

$$\underline{T}_o^S \leq T_{o,t}^S \leq \overline{T}_o^S, \quad \underline{T}_o^R \leq T_{o,t}^R \leq \overline{R}_o^S, \forall o, t, \quad (1z)$$

$$T_{o,v,t}^{S,\text{in}} = T_{o,t}^S, \quad T_{o,v,t}^{R,\text{in}} = T_{v,t}^R, \quad \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, t, \quad (1aa)$$

$$T_{v,t}^S = T_{o,v,t}^{S,\text{out}}, \quad T_{o,t}^R = T_{o,v,t}^{R,\text{out}}, \quad \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, t, \quad (1ab)$$

$$-M v_{o,v,\eta,t}^S \leq \tilde{T}_{o,v,\eta,t}^{S,\text{in}} \leq M v_{o,v,\eta,t}^S, \quad \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, \eta \in \{0, \dots, \overline{\tau}_{o,v}^S\}, t, \quad (1ac)$$

$$M(v_{o,v,\eta,t}^S - 1) \leq \tilde{T}_{o,v,\eta,t}^{S,\text{in}} - \tilde{T}_{o,v,(t-\eta)}^{S,\text{in}} \left(1 - \frac{2\mu_{o,v}}{c\rho R_{o,v}}\eta\right) \leq M(1 - v_{o,v,\eta,t}^S), \quad \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, \eta \in \{0, \dots, \overline{\tau}_{o,v}^S\}, t, \quad (1ad)$$

$$M(v_{o,v,\eta,t}^S - 1) \leq \eta - \tau_{o,v,t}^S \leq M(1 - v_{o,v,\eta,t}^S), \quad \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, \eta \in \{0, \dots, \overline{\tau}_{o,v}^S\}, t, \quad (1ae)$$

$$\sum_{\eta=0}^{\overline{\tau}^S} v_{o,v,\eta,t}^S = 1, \quad \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, t, \quad (1af)$$

$$T_{o,v,t}^{S,\text{out}} = \sum_{\eta=0}^{\overline{\tau}_{o,v}^S} \tilde{T}_{o,v,\eta,t}^{S,\text{in}}, \quad \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, t, \quad (1ag)$$

$$-M v_{o,v,\eta,t}^S \leq \tilde{T}_{o,v,\eta,t}^{S,\text{in}} \leq M v_{o,v,\eta,t}^S, \quad \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, \eta \in \{0, \dots, \overline{\tau}_{o,v}^S\}, t, \quad (1ah)$$

$$M(v_{o,v,\eta,t}^S - 1) \leq \tilde{T}_{o,v,\eta,t}^{S,\text{in}} - \tilde{T}_{o,v,(t-\eta)}^{S,\text{in}} \left(1 - \frac{2\mu_{o,v}}{c\rho R_{o,v}}\eta\right) \leq M(1 - v_{o,v,\eta,t}^S), \quad \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, \eta \in \{0, \dots, \overline{\tau}_{o,v}^S\}, t, \quad (1ai)$$

$$M(v_{o,v,\eta,t}^S - 1) \leq \eta - \tau_{o,v,t}^S \leq M(1 - v_{o,v,\eta,t}^S), \quad \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, \eta \in \{0, \dots, \overline{\tau}_{o,v}^S\}, t, \quad (1aj)$$

$$\sum_{\eta=0}^{\overline{\tau}^S} v_{o,v,\eta,t}^S = 1, \quad \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, t, \quad (1ak)$$

$$T_{o,v,t}^{S,\text{out}} = \sum_{\eta=0}^{\overline{\tau}_{o,v}^S} \tilde{T}_{o,v,\eta,t}^{S,\text{in}}, \quad \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, t, \quad (1al)$$

$$M(u_{o,v,\eta,t}^S - 1) \leq \sum_{\tilde{\eta}=t-\eta}^t \frac{mf_{o,v,\tilde{\eta}}^S}{\pi R_{o,v}^2 \rho} \Delta t - L_{o,v} \leq M u_{o,v,\eta,t}^S, \quad \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, \eta \in \{0, \dots, \overline{\tau}_{o,v}^S\}, t, \quad (1am)$$

$$M(u_{o,v,\eta,t}^R - 1) \leq \sum_{\tilde{\eta}=t-\eta}^t \frac{mf_{o,v,\tilde{\eta}}^R}{\pi R_{o,v}^2 \rho} \Delta t - L_{o,v} \leq M u_{o,v,\eta,t}^R, \quad \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, \eta \in \{0, \dots, \overline{\tau}_{o,v}^R\}, t, \quad (1an)$$

$$\tau_{o,v,t}^S = \sum_{\eta=1}^{\overline{\tau}_{o,v}^S} \eta(u_{o,v,\eta,t}^S - u_{o,v,(\eta-1),t}^S), \quad \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, t, \quad (1ao)$$

$$\tau_{o,v,t}^R = \sum_{\eta=1}^{\overline{\tau}_{o,v}^R} \eta(u_{o,v,\eta,t}^R - u_{o,v,(\eta-1),t}^R), \quad \forall (o,v) \in \mathcal{P}, t, \quad (1ap)$$

$$0 \leq g_{k,t} \leq \overline{g}_k, \quad \forall k, t, \quad (1aq)$$

$$\underline{pr}_m \leq pr_{m,t} \leq \overline{pr}_m, \quad \forall m, t, \quad (1ar)$$

$$pr_{u,t} \leq \Gamma_{m,u} pr_{m,t}, \quad \forall (m,u) \in \mathcal{Z}, t, \quad (1as)$$

$$q_{m,u,t}^2 \leq K_{m,u}^2 (pr_{m,t}^2 - pr_{u,t}^2), \quad \forall (m,u) \in \mathcal{Z}, t, \quad (1at)$$

$$q_{m,u,t} = \frac{q_{m,u,t}^{\text{in}} + q_{m,u,t}^{\text{out}}}{2}, \quad \forall (m,u) \in \mathcal{Z}, t, \quad (1au)$$

$$h_{m,u,t} = S_{m,u} \frac{pr_{m,t} + pr_{u,t}}{2}, \quad \forall (m,u) \in \mathcal{Z}, t, \quad (1av)$$

$$h_{m,u,t} = h_{m,u,(t-1)} + q_{m,u,t}^{\text{in}} - q_{m,u,t}^{\text{out}}, \forall (m,u) \in \mathcal{Z}, t > 1, \quad (1aw)$$

$$h_{m,u,t} = H_{m,u}^0 + q_{m,u,t}^{\text{in}} - q_{m,u,t}^{\text{out}}, \forall (m,u) \in \mathcal{Z}, t = 1, \quad (1ax)$$

$$H_{m,u}^0 \leq h_{m,u,t}, \forall (m,u) \in \mathcal{Z}, t = |\mathcal{T}|, \quad (1ay)$$

$$\sum_{k \in \mathcal{A}_m^K} g_{k,t} - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}_m^G} \phi_i p_{i,t} - \sum_{u:(m,u) \in \mathcal{Z}} (q_{m,u,t}^{\text{in}} - q_{u,m,t}^{\text{out}}) = D_{m,t}^G, \forall m, t, \quad (1az)$$

$$r_i Q_{i,t} \leq p_{i,t}, \forall i \in \mathcal{CHP}, t, \quad (1ba)$$

$$0 \leq \rho_i^E p_{i,t} + \rho_i^H Q_{i,t} \leq \bar{p}_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{CHP}, t, \quad (1bb)$$

$$Q_{i,t} = COP_i D_{i,t}^{\text{HP}}, \forall i \in \mathcal{HP}, t, \quad (1bc)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}_n^I} p_{i,t} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{A}_n^J} w_{j,t} - \sum_{r:(n,r) \in \mathcal{L}} f_{n,r,t} = D_{n,t}^E + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}_n^{\text{HP}}} D_{i,t}^{\text{HP}}, \forall n, t. \quad (1bd)$$

2. INPUT DATA

Fig. 1 illustrates the power network and Figs. 2 and 3 the natural gas and heat network, respectively. In addition, Table 1 gives the technical characteristics of power generators and transmission lines, Table 2 provides the technical characteristics of the gas system and Table 3 contains the input data for the heat network.

FIGURE 1. 24-bus power system

FIGURE 2. 12-node natural gas network

FIGURE 3. 3-bus heat network

Generator i	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12						
Located at bus n	1	2	7	13	15	15	16	18	21	22	23	23						
Connected to gas node m	12	12	-	-	10	10	7	-	-	6	-	-						
Connected to heat node o	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2						
C_i^E [\$/MWh]	-	-	65.61	30.82	-	-	-	20.84	26.9	-	32.22	-						
C_i [\$/MWh]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	17.5						
\bar{p}_i [MW]	152	152	300	591	60	155	155	400	400	300	350	1000						
Type	\mathcal{G}	\mathcal{G}	\mathcal{C}	\mathcal{C}	\mathcal{G}	\mathcal{G}	\mathcal{G}	\mathcal{C}	\mathcal{C}	\mathcal{G}	\mathcal{C}	\mathcal{CHP}						
ϕ_i [kcf/MWh]	12.65	20.25	-	-	11.12	15.1	14.88	-	-	13.3	-	-						
Wind farm j	1																	
Located at bus n	5																	
\bar{W}_j [MW]	2100																	
Power load	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
At bus n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	13	14	15	16	18	19	20	23
Share of total load	0.038	0.044	0.063	0.026	0.025	0.048	0.044	0.060	0.061	0.068	0.093	0.073	0.111	0.035	0.117	0.014	0.04	0.04
Line $(n,r) \in \mathcal{L}$	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
n	1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	5	6	7	8	8	9	9	10	10	11
r	2	3	5	4	6	9	24	9	10	10	8	9	10	11	12	11	12	13
$1/B_{n,r}$ [pu]	0.0146	0.2253	0.0907	0.1356	0.205	0.1271	0.084	0.111	0.094	0.0642	0.0652	0.1762	0.1762	0.084	0.084	0.084	0.084	0.0488
$\bar{f}_{n,r}$ [MW]	175	175	350	175	175	175	400	175	350	175	350	175	175	400	400	400	400	500
Line $(n,r) \in \mathcal{L}$	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34		
n	11	12	12	13	14	15	15	15	16	16	17	17	18	19	20	21		
r	14	13	23	23	16	16	21	24	17	19	18	22	21	20	23	22		
$1/B_{n,r}$ [pu]	0.0426	0.0488	0.0985	0.0884	0.0594	0.0172	0.0249	0.0529	0.0263	0.0234	0.0143	0.1069	0.0132	0.0203	0.0112	0.0692		
$\bar{f}_{n,r}$ [MW]	500	500	500	250	250	500	400	500	500	500	500	500	1000	1000	1000	500		

TABLE 1. Power system input data for generators, wind farms, loads and transmission lines

Gas supplier k	1	2	3									
Located at node m	1	3	11									
\bar{g}_k [kcf]	7200	7200	18000									
C_k^G [\$/kcf]	2	2.4	3.2									
Demand	1	2	3	4								
At node m	5	6	7	12								
Share of total demand	0.25	0.35	0.25	0.15								
Pipeline $(m, u) \in \mathcal{Z}$	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
m	1	2	3	4	5	4	6	7	8	9	10	11
u	2	4	5	5	6	7	8	8	9	10	11	12
$K_{m,u}$ [kcf/psig h]	28	28	28	21	21	21	28	21	28	28	28	28
$\Gamma_{m,u}$	-	1.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.3	-	-	-
$S_{m,u}$ [kcf/psig]	121	121	150	186	189	184	150	179	149	148	150	130
$H_{m,u}^0$ [kcf]	39300	39300	49300	59300	54300	54300	39300	44300	39300	39300	39300	29300

TABLE 2. Input data for gas system. Note that minimum and maximum pressure limits \underline{pr}_m and \bar{pr}_m are 100 psig and 500 psig for all nodes m , respectively.

Heat unit i	CHP	HP	
Located at node o	1	2	
\bar{Q}_i [MW]	250	150	
$\overline{mf}_i^{\text{HS}}$ [kg/h]	0	0	
$\underline{mf}_i^{\text{HS}}$ [kg/h]	300	300	
COP_i	-	2.5	
r_i	0.6	-	
ρ_i^E	2.4	-	
ρ_i^H	0.25	-	
C_i [\$/MWh]	17.5	-	
Node o	1	2	3
$\overline{mf}_o^{\text{HES}}$ [kg/h]	-	-	50
$\underline{mf}_o^{\text{HES}}$ [kg/h]	-	-	300
\underline{T}_o^R [C]	30	30	30
\bar{T}_o^R [C]	60	60	60
\underline{T}_o^S [C]	90	90	90
\bar{T}_o^S [C]	120	120	120
$pr_o^{S/R}$ [psig]	0	0	0
$\bar{pr}_o^{S/R}$ [psig]	100	100	100
Pipeline $(o, v) \in \mathcal{P}$	1	2	
o	1	2	
v	2	3	
$R_{o,v}$ [m]	2	3	
$\mu_{o,v}$ [MW m ⁻² K ⁻¹]	20	20	
$\nu_{o,v}$ [10 ⁻³]	1.93	1.93	
$\overline{mf}_{o,v}^{S/R}$ [kg/h]	50	50	
$\underline{mf}_{o,v}^{S/R}$ [kg/h]	300	300	

TABLE 3. District heating system characteristics. Note that $c=1.17$ Wh/(kg K), $\rho=988$ kg/m³.